

Conference Abstract

Decadal analysis of chlorophyll fluorescence, algal blooms and driving factors from a fixed-point observing system in the Northern Adriatic Sea

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Abstract

Understanding the dynamics of coastal marine ecosystems is fundamental for assessing environmental health and addressing anthropogenic impacts. This study analyzes a decade-long dataset of high-resolution Chlorophyll fluorescence (ChlF) measurements collected hourly from August 2012 to December 2022 at the E1 meteo-oceanographic buoy (Bohm et al. 2016). The buoy is located in the Northern Adriatic Sea (44° 08.58' N; 12° 34.20' E), approximately 100 km south of the Po River delta and 7 km northeast of Rimini, Italy. As part of the “Delta del Po and Costa Romagnola” (Bergami and Riminucci 2025) research site within the Italian LTER network and the PNRR ITINERIS project, the E1 station provides a unique platform for multidisciplinary research and long-term environmental monitoring.

ChlF data, collected by the WET Labs[®] ECO Triplet (now SeaBird Scientific), reveal significant seasonal and interannual variations in chlorophyll concentration, estimates

from in situ ChIF, ranging from below detection limits to a maximum daily average of 41 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Together with ChIF, other meteorological, chemical, and physical parameters such as temperature (TEMP), dissolved oxygen (DO), salinity (SAL), turbidity (TURB), and wind speed (WS) were incorporated for this study (Riminucci et al. 2024, Riminucci et al. 2025). A total of 40 distinct algal bloom events were identified using ChIF concentration thresholds and growth rate dynamics (Trombetta et al. 2019). The analysis of bloom frequency revealed two main periods of bloom events per year (Fig. 1), with the identified blooms lasting an average of 13 ± 10 days. During these events, ChIF concentration increased to an average of $6.5 \mu\text{g/L}$, indicating substantial algal growth, compared to a baseline of $2.8 \mu\text{g/L}$ observed outside bloom periods. The most intense blooms occurred in spring, driven by nutrient inputs and increased sunlight, while summer blooms were weaker, less frequent, and shorter in duration due to thermal stratification. In contrast, autumn and winter saw a resurgence of bloom activity, influenced by freshwater inflow, nutrient resuspension, and strong mixing. These seasonal patterns underscore the dynamic interplay between temperature, wind, and nutrient availability in shaping phytoplankton dynamics.

Figure 1. [doi](#)

Daily average ChIF data in 10 years dataset, in green are the identified algal bloom events.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted to identify key relationships among environmental variables and their influence on algal blooms (Fig. 2). The strong correlation between ChIF and DO during bloom periods reflects the role of photosynthesis in elevating oxygen levels. TEMP and SAL are linked due to seasonal stratification, while WS and TURB highlight wind-driven physical disturbances, such as sediment resuspension and waves. Overall, PCA captures both seasonal and biological processes, including bloom dynamics, as well as physical disturbances driven by wind

and water movement. Seasonal factors govern bloom dynamics, with spring and late autumn/winter supporting phytoplankton growth due to favourable nutrient availability and stable conditions, while summer stratification limits blooms. These findings underscore the interplay of biological and physical drivers in shaping the ecosystem response over the decade.

Figure 2. [doi](#)

PCA core circle plot for PC1 vs. PC2 (left) and PC2 vs. PC3 (right), with bloom events in brown and non-bloom days in black.

Two bloom types were identified: Single-Peak Blooms, typical in spring, characterized by rapid growth and short durations, and Multi-Peak Blooms, more common in autumn, with extended periods due to intermittent nutrient apportionment. Nutrient-rich freshwater inputs from the Po River, nitrogen and phosphorus, and seasonal cycles of phytoplankton play a significant role in driving these blooms. Diatoms such as *Skeletonema marinoi* dominate the winter bloom, while spring and autumn blooms are diatom-driven, modulated by rainfall and nutrient runoff (Grilli et al. 2020, Totti et al. 2019). Summer, characterized by water column stratification, generally exhibits lower ChlF concentrations unless disturbed by storms or mixing events that reintroduce nutrients into surface waters. These findings emphasize the complex seasonal and environmental drivers shaping bloom dynamics.

This study introduces a methodological framework for detecting coastal algal blooms by analyzing patterns derived from in-situ fluorescence measurements, offering insights into bloom dynamics. While challenges such as data gaps due to sensor maintenance and biofouling, the findings underscore the value of long-term, high-frequency observations in understanding environmental processes and managing coastal ecosystems. Future research should focus on integrating complementary datasets, such as nutrient concentrations or satellite observations, to deepen the understanding of bloom drivers. Additionally, expanding datasets temporally, by including more years, and spatially, by incorporating other monitoring systems (e.g., fixed-point stations), will further enhance the robustness and applicability of the framework.

Keywords

Chlorophyll fluorescence; fixed-point observing systems; Northern Adriatic Sea; LTER; algal blooms; environmental drivers; seasonal patterns

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Bergami C, Riminucci F (2025) DEIMS.iD "Delta del Po e Costa Romagnola - Italy". <https://deims.org/6869436a-80f4-4c6d-954b-a730b348d7ce>
- Böhm E, Riminucci F, Bortoluzzi G, Colella S, F. A, Santoleri R, Ravaioli M, et al. (2016) Operational use of continuous surface fluorescence measurements offshore Rimini to

- validate satellite-derived chlorophyll observations. *Journal of Operational Oceanography* 9 <https://doi.org/10.1080/1755876X.2015.1117763>
- Grilli F, Accoroni S, Acri F, Bernardi Aubry F, Bergami C, Cabrini M, Campanelli A, Giani M, Guicciardi S, Marini M (2020) Seasonal and Interannual Trends of Oceanographic Parameters over 40 Years in the Northern Adriatic Sea in Relation to Nutrient Loadings Using the EMODnet Chemistry Data Portal. *Water* 12 (8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12082280>
 - Riminucci F, Bergami C, Bohm E, Bortoluzzi G, Capotondi L, Correggiari A, Focaccia P, Gallerani A, Ravaioli M, Sanstoleri R, Stanghellini G, Toller S (2024) Salinity, Turbidity, Wind from the E1 buoy at the LTER site Delta del Po and Costa Romagnola (2012-2021) [Data set]. Zenodo. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10980386>
 - Riminucci F, Bergami C, Bohm E, Bortoluzzi G, Capotondi L, Correggiari A, Focaccia P, Gallerani A, Ravaioli M, Santoleri R, Stanghellini G, Toller S (2025) Sea Temperature, Dissolved Oxygen, Chlorophyll-a from the E1 buoy at the LTER site Delta del Po and Costa Romagnola (2012-2022) [Data set]. Zenodo. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14748898>
 - Totti C, Romagnoli T, Accoroni S, Coluccelli A, Pellegrini M, Campanelli A, Grilli F, Marini M (2019) Phytoplankton communities in the northwestern Adriatic Sea: Interdecadal variability over a 30-years period (1988–2016) and relationships with meteorological drivers. *Journal of Marine Systems* 193: 137-153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2019.01.007>
 - Trombetta T, Vidussi F, Mas S, Parin D, Simier M, Mostajir B (2019) Water temperature drives phytoplankton blooms in coastal waters. *PLoS ONE* 14 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0214933>